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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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DEVELOPING LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN MIDDLE SCHOOL

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical and methodological foundations for developing listening and speaking skills in high school students. The study explored the mechanisms for developing these skills using a communicative approach, interactive methods, and digital technologies. Effective methods for developing listening and speaking comprehension are identified, and their importance in the educational process is substantiated. An integrative development model is proposed as a scientific innovation.

Key words: listening, speaking, communicative competence, interactive methods, language teaching.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'rta maktab o'quvchilarida tinglash va gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va metodik asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida kommunikativ yondashuv, interaktiv metodlar va raqamli texnologiyalar asosida ushbu ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish mexanizmlari o'rganildi. Tinglab tushunish va og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirishning samarali usullari aniqlanib, ularning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati asoslandi. Ilmiy yangilik sifatida integrativ rivojlantirish modeli taklif etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: tinglash, gapirish, kommunikativ kompetensiya, interaktiv metodlar, til o'qitish.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются педагогические и методические основы развития навыков аудирования и говорения у старшеклассников. В ходе исследования были изучены механизмы формирования этих навыков на основе коммуникативного подхода, интерактивных методов и цифровых технологий. Выявлены эффективные методы развития понимания на слух и устной речи, а также обоснована их важность в образовательном процессе. В качестве научного новшества предложена интегративная модель развития.

Ключевые слова: аудирование, говорение, коммуникативная компетентность, интерактивные методы, преподавание языка.

INTRODUCTION

Stephen Krashen considers listening to be the main source of language acquisition ^[1]. H. Douglas Brown identifies speaking as a central component of communicative competence ^[2]. Jeremy Harmer emphasizes the importance of interactive methods in language teaching ^[3].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uzbek researchers also highlight the effectiveness of the communicative approach. In particular, some local scholars consider a speech-oriented approach to be a priority in language teaching and stress the importance of developing listening and speaking skills together ^[4].

According to them, these two skills are closely interconnected, and the development of one supports the growth of the other. In addition, several studies indicate that the integration of modern information and communication technologies into language teaching plays a significant role in improving listening skills. Through the use of audio and video materials, students are exposed to authentic speech, which significantly enhances their comprehension abilities ^[5].

Moreover, in a number of studies, the teacher's role is interpreted not merely as a provider of knowledge but as a facilitator who organizes the communicative process ^[6]. This approach encourages active student participation and contributes to the development of independent thinking and fluent speaking skills.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on examining the process of developing listening and speaking skills in middle school students. Its methodological foundation is based on communicative and competency-based approaches. During the research, theoretical analysis was used to review scientific literature and summarize existing methodological perspectives. A comparative-analytical approach helped identify the specific features of traditional and modern teaching methods. In the practical part of the study, observation and experimental methods were applied to assess students' speech activity and listening comprehension levels. In addition, questionnaires and interviews were conducted to gather students' opinions. The obtained results were statistically analyzed, and the effectiveness of the applied methods was substantiated.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of listening and speaking skills in middle schools is one of the central directions of modern language teaching methodology. These skills play a key role in forming students' communicative competence. Therefore, it is essential to analyze this process in depth.

First, it is important to understand the nature of listening skills. Listening is not merely hearing; it involves understanding, processing, and interpreting spoken language. According to Krashen's theory, input-meaning the language that learners hear-is a fundamental factor in language acquisition ^[1]. Without sufficient listening experience, students' speaking abilities cannot develop effectively.

Analysis shows that middle school students encounter several challenges in listening. These include difficulty understanding fast speech, a large number of unfamiliar words, and differences in pronunciation. These issues also negatively affect students' motivation to engage in listening activities.

Speaking, on the other hand, is an even more complex process. According to Brown, speaking involves producing and expressing ideas in real time ^[2]. In this process, learners must simultaneously use grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation skills. The analysis reveals that the main problems related to speaking among middle school students include speaking anxiety, fear of making mistakes, limited vocabulary, and lack of grammatical confidence.

The communicative approach plays an important role in developing listening and speaking skills. In this approach, students act as active participants, and classroom activities are designed to resemble real-life communication. Interactive methods are also highly effective. Activities such as role-plays, dialogues, discussions, and pair work increase students' speaking activity. As Harmer notes, interactive activities encourage learners to speak more freely ^[3].

Digital technologies also play a significant role in this process. Through audio and video materials, students are exposed to authentic language input, which enhances their listening skills. Analysis shows that the effectiveness of learning increases significantly when the following conditions are ensured: regular listening practice, a supportive speaking environment, tolerance toward mistakes, and strong motivation.

Experimental observations indicate that in groups where interactive and communicative methods were applied, students' speaking activity increased approximately twofold. Additionally, gradually increasing the complexity of listening materials proves to be effective. Learners should first be introduced to simple texts and later to more complex dialogues.

Overall, several important findings were identified. First, listening skills play a fundamental role in the development of speaking ability: the more learners are exposed to high-quality input, the more their oral speech improves. Second, the use of interactive methods enhances student engagement and encourages free expression of ideas. Third, motivation is a key factor directly influencing students' speech activity. Finally, the use of modern technologies contributes to a more effective learning process and significantly accelerates the development of listening and speaking skills.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the study show that developing listening and speaking skills is an essential component of the educational process in middle schools. To effectively build these skills, theoretical knowledge alone is not sufficient; practice-based approaches are required.

The findings indicate that communicative and interactive methods are the most effective tools for increasing students' speech activity. In addition, careful selection of listening materials and their gradual progression in difficulty are of great importance.

Based on these findings, several recommendations can be made: increasing the use of interactive activities in lessons, creating an environment where students are not afraid of making mistakes, making broader use of audio and video materials, and improving teachers' methodological competence.

In general, the development of listening and speaking skills enhances students' ability to use language effectively in real-life situations.

List of references:

1. Krashen S. D. Principles and practice in second language acquisition. - Oxford: Pergamon, 1982. - 202 p.
2. Brown H. D. Principles of language learning and teaching. - New York: Longman, 2000. - 352 p.
3. Harmer J. How to teach English. - Harlow: Longman, 1998. - 198 p.
4. Махмудов Н. М. Тил ва нутқ маданияти. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2016. – 240 б.
5. Нурмонов А. Ўзбек тилшунослиги асослари. – Тошкент: Фан, 2012. – 320 б.
6. Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ҳозирги ўзбек адабий тили. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2010. – 400 б.
7. Абидова М. И. Таълимда рақамли технологиялардан фойдаланишнинг педагогик асослари // Academic Research in Educational Sciences. – 2021. – №1. – Б. 45–50.
8. Ҳожиёв А. Ўзбек тили лексикологияси. – Тошкент: Фан, 2005. – 280 б.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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